

Analytical Uses of Nessler's Reagent. Quantitative Estimation of Monosaccharides and Disaccharides. Estimation of Furfural. Part II.

By M. GOSWAMI AND B. C. DAS-PURKAYSTHA.

It has been shown by one of us in a previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 714) that Nessler's reagent can be used successfully to distinguish ketones from aldehydes, all of which latter reduce it, the only exception being *o*-hydroxy-aldehydes and hydroxy-ketones which show anomaly that can be otherwise explained. It has also been shown that by replacing sodium hydroxide by sodium carbonate, glucose can be directly estimated quantitatively without recourse to an intermediate standard. This method has now been extended for the estimation of other monosaccharides and disaccharides. A preliminary note on the estimation of fructose and cane sugar has already been published (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **13**, 73).

The reaction between glucose and K_2HgI_4 is evidently one of reduction of the latter first to Hg_2I_2 and thence to metallic Hg as follows :—

This liberated I_2 corresponding to one mercury and one oxygen atom is utilised to oxidise glucose. The principle of the method is based on the estimation of the liberated mercury, the amount of which denotes the degree of reducibility of glucose. It has been shown that under the standard conditions prescribed, one glucose molecule takes up two atoms of oxygen *i.e.*, liberates two atoms of mercury. It was also indicated that the reducibility of fructose proceeds further than that of glucose. This has now been established. It has been found that under the standard conditions prescribed the following are the respective proportions of oxygen which are utilised to oxidise the principal mono- and disaccharides

1 mol. Arabinose	...	1 atom of oxygen.	Table I
Glucose	...	2 atoms	
2 Fructose	...	5	II and III
2 Cane sugar	...	9	IV
2 Lactose	...	5	V
2 Maltose	...	5	VI

In the case of furfural sodium hydroxide has been used instead of sodium carbonate which gives low results and it has been found that in this case one molecule requires one atom of oxygen (Table VII).

For the purpose of standardising our method we have taken 'Difco' and 'Analar' standard of sugars and Kahlbaum's purest sugars for calorimetric estimations. Before preparing the solutions the sugars have been dried in *vacuo* at 80-90° for 1 hour. The melting points were then checked. We have reasons to think that even with such precautions we were unable to get 100% pure sugars and this will perhaps explain the slight variations from the theoretical values.

It was thought worth while to extend the method to estimate minute quantities of glucose (0.1 g. in 100 c. c.) using very small quantities of reagents. Table VIII will show that the results are satisfactory. This micro-estimation was then extended to the determinations of sugar in blood. Tables IX and X will show that this new micro-estimation method compares very favourably with the other recognised methods of which no two methods give identical results even for the same sample of blood.*

Further applications of Nessler's reagent for the quantitative estimation of (aromatic and aliphatic) aldehydes (saturated and olefinic) are in progress.

* Quantitative Clinical Chemistry by Peters and Van Slyke, Vol. II, p. 455 and *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1929, **83**, 51.

	Miligram of sugar for 100 c. c. of blood compared with that by Benedict's method taken as 100.		
	Average.	Maximum.	Minimum.
Method Shaffer-Hartman's Somogyi-copper titration method. <i>J. Biol. Chem.</i> , 1926, 70 , 599	121	149	109
Folin Ferricyanide colorimetric method. <i>J. Biol. Chem.</i> , 1928, 77 , 421 ; 1929, 81 , 231	98	124	86
Van Slyke Hawkin's Ferricyanide gasometric and timing method. <i>J. Biol. Chem.</i> , 1929, 85 , 69 ; 1929, 83 , 51	120	138	115

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Potassium mercuric iodide used in the following experiments had the following composition :

HgCl ₂	...	...	2.5 g.
KI	...	...	8 g.
Water	...	...	100 c. c.

10% Na₂CO₃ solution and Kahlbaum's purest glacial acetic acid (without any iodine value) have been used throughout except in the case of furfural where sodium carbonate had been replaced by caustic soda

General Procedure.—Sugar solution was mixed with potassium mercuric iodide solution (25-35 c. c.) in a litre flask and to this Na₂CO₃ solution (50 c. c.) was added. The mixed solution was boiled (8-10 minutes) until grey metallic mercury deposited at the bottom and the supernatant liquid became clear. The flask was then cooled, glacial acetic acid (15 c. c.) added and excess of standard iodine solution (25-50 c. c.) poured in and the contents thoroughly shaken till mercury went completely into the solution. The excess of iodine was then titrated back with standard thiosulphate. The following table gives results with arabinose.

TABLE I.

Arabinose.

Arabinose soln. taken = 5 c.c. 50 C. c. of 0.9979N/10-I₂ soln. added. Conc of hypo = 0.9951N/10.

Arabinose.	Volume of hypo required		Arabinose found (A-B) × hypo conc. × 0.0075.	Present.
	Before oxidation. A.	After oxidation. B.		
0.6922 g./100 c.c.	50.15 c.c.	45.4 c.c.	0.03545 g.	0.03461 g.
0.6922	50.15	45.5	0.03470	0.03461
0.6262	50.15	46.0	0.03096	0.03131
0.6262	50.15	45.95	0.03134	0.03131
0.3461	25.1	22.8	0.01716	0.017305
0.3461	25.1	22.8	0.01716	0.017305

TABLE II.

Laevulose.

Conc = 1.5750 g. in 250 c. c. Vol. taken = 10 c. c.
50 C. c. of 1.052N - I₂ soln. added

1.0676 N/10-hypo required		Laevulose	
Before oxidation A	After oxidation. B	(A - B) × 1.0676 × 0.0036	Present.
49.3 c.c.	32.9 c.c.	0.06302 g	0.063 g.
49.3	32.85	0.06322	0.063
49.3	32.95	0.06284	0.063
49.3	32.9	0.06302	0.063

TABLE III.

Laevulose.

50 C. c. of I₂ soln. added

Laevulose (g / 100 c.c.)	Vol	Conc. of I ₂ soln (N/10)	Volume of hypo required		Conc of hypo (N/10) C	Found (A - B) × C × 0.0036	Present
			Before oxidation A.	After oxidation B			
0.8327	5 c.c.	0.6342	32.2 c.c.	20.45 c.c.	0.9846	0.04166g.	0.04164g.
0.8327	5	0.6342	32.2	20.5	0.9846	0.04148	0.04164
0.7082	5	0.6342	32.2	22.2	0.9846	0.03545	0.03541
0.7082	5	0.6342	32.2	22.25	0.9846	0.03527	0.03541
0.4593	10	0.9979	50.15	37.55	0.9951	0.04513	0.04593
0.4593	10	0.9979	50.15	37.45	0.9951	0.04548	0.04593

It has been found that best results are obtained within 1.05% concentration. The amount of sodium carbonate solution is important, as with lesser quantities than those prescribed low results are obtained.

In the case of cane sugar, it was hydrolysed by hydrochloric acid in the usual way and the acid was then neutralised by sodium carbonate solution. The estimation was then done with this hydrolysed product giving the following results.

TABLE IV.

*Cane sugar.*5 C.c. of cane sugar soln. and 50 c. c. of I₂ soln. added.

Cane sugar (g./100 c.c.).	Conc of I ₂ soln. (N/10).	Vol. of Hypo required		Conc. of hypo (N/10) C.	Cane sugar	
		Before oxidation A.	After oxidation B.		Found (A - B) × C × 0.0038.	Present.
0.8082	0.9979	50.15 c.c.	39.45 c.c.	0.9951	0.04046 g.	0.04041 g.
0.8082	0.9979	50.15	39.55	0.9951	0.04007	0.04041
0.7892	1.161	58.7	48.25	0.9897	0.03930	0.03946
0.7892	1.161	58.7	48.3	0.9897	0.03911	0.03946
0.7616	1.169	61.9	51.4	0.9445	0.03769	0.03808
0.7616	1.169	61.9	51.35	0.9445	0.03787	0.03808
0.5044	1.169	61.9	54.9	0.9445	0.02513	0.02522
0.5044	1.169	61.9	54.9	0.9445	0.02513	0.02522

Both lactose and maltose contain one molecule of water of crystallisation which is only expelled by heating at 135-140° for about an hour but during this heating the substance partially carbonises. Hence vacuum heating was restored to as described before. The following tables give the results obtained.

TABLE V.

*Lactose.*10 C.c. of lactose solution and 50 c. c. of 0.9972 N/10-I₂ soln. added. Conc. of hypo = 0.9776N/10.

Lactose	Volume of hypo required		Lactose	
	Before oxidation A.	After oxidation B.	(A - B) × strength of hypo × 0.0684.	Present.
0.8166 g./100 c.c.	51 c.c.	39 c.c.	0.08026 g.	0.08166 g.
0.8166	51	39	0.08026	0.08166
0.6848	51	40.85	0.06797	0.06848
0.6848	51	40.8	0.06822	0.06848
0.5226	51	43.2	0.05217	0.05226
0.5226	51	43.3	0.05150	0.05226

TABLE VI.

Maltose.

10 C.c. maltose solution and 50 c.c. of 1.0495 N/10-iodine added.
 Conc. of hypo = 1.015 N/10.

Maltose.	Volume of hypo Before oxidation A.	required After oxidation B.	Maltose Found (A - B) × strength of hypo × 0.00684.	Present.
0.84856 g./100 c.c.	51.7 c.c.	39.45 c.c.	0.08504 g.	0.084856 g.
0.84856	51.7	39.5	0.08470	0.084856
0.6348	51.7	42.55	0.06352	0.06348
0.6348	51.7	42.6	0.06317	0.06348
0.4544	51.7	45.15	0.04546	0.04544
0.4544	51.7	45.25	0.04478	0.04544

In the case of furfural Merck's pro-analysis product was taken, dried overnight with anhydrous sodium sulphate and redistilled. The general procedure was the same as that described before with the exception that caustic soda (10%) solution was used instead of sodium carbonate solution.

TABLE VII.

Furfural.

50 C.c. of 1.002 N/10-I₂-soln. added and 1.018 N/10-hypo used.

Furfural.	Vol.	Volume of hypo Before oxidation A.	required After oxidation B.	Furfural Found (A - B) × strength of hypo × 0.0048.	Present.
1.7484 g./100 c.c.	5 c.c.	49.25 c.c.	31.65 c.c.	0.08596 g.	0.08742 g.
1.7484	5	49.25	31.6	0.08601	0.08742
1.1027	10	49.25	26.75	0.1099	0.11027
1.1027	10	49.25	26.75	0.1099	0.11027
0.8673	10	49.25	31.5	0.0867	0.08673
0.8673	10	49.25	31.6	0.0862	0.08673

This method of estimation of furfural has been found to give good results in presence of acetone (private communication from Dr. H. K. Sen).

Micro-estimation of glucose gave the following results.

TABLE VIII.

Micro-estimation of glucose.

Volume of glucose solution (0.1116 g. in 100 c.c.) used = 0.1 c.c.
1.0126 N/100 iodine added = 2 c.c. 1.0126 N/100-hypo used.

Volume of hypo required Before oxidation A.	Volume of hypo required After oxidation B.	Glucose found (A-B) $\times$ 1.0126 $\times$ 0.00045.	Glucose present.
2 c.c.	1.76 c.c.	0.0001093 g.	0.0001116 g.
2	1.75	0.0001139	0.0001116
2	1.76	0.0001093	0.0001116

In the case of estimation of blood sugar by the micromethod described above, the blood was deproteinised according to the principles of Somogyi's method (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1930, **86**, 655). Blood (0.1 c.c.) was mixed with a mixture of zinc sulphate (5 c.c. of 0.45%) and KOH solution (1 c.c. of N/10). The mixture was heated for 4 minutes by immersing in water-bath and filtered through a small filter. The filter paper was then washed twice with warm water (in 3 c.c. portions). To this 1 c.c. of potassium mercuric iodide solution (previous concentration diluted 10 times) and 2 c.c. of sodium carbonate solution (1%) were added. The mixture was heated in the usual way in a test tube (for 10 minutes), cooled, acidified with pure acetic acid solution (2 c.c. of 3%). 2 C.c. of N/100-iodine solution were then added and the test-tube shaken and the excess of iodine was titrated back with dilute thiosulphate solution using micro pipette and micro burette. The following are the results.

TABLE IX.

Blood sugar.

Vol. of blood taken = 0.1 c.c. Vol. of Iodine solution added = 1 c.c.

Conc. of I ₂	Volume of hypo required Before oxidation A.	Volume of hypo required After oxidation B.	Conc. of hypo.	Sugar in blood (A-B) × strength × 0.225.
1.0126 N/100	2 c.c.	1.4 c.c.	1.0126 N/200	0.1367 %
1.0126 N/100	2	1.4	1.0126 N/200	0.1367
1.9998 N/200	1.98	1.38	1.01 N/200	0.1363
1.9998 N/200	1.98	1.395	1.01 N/200	0.1329
1.8959 N/200	1.83	1.39	1.036 N/200	0.1026
1.8959 N/200	1.83	1.39	1.036 N/200	0.1026

Hagendorn and Jenson's potassium ferricyanide method of estimation of blood sugar gave the following results with the same samples of blood.

TABLE X.

Blood sugar.

Vol. of blood taken = 0.1 c.c. Vol. of 0.1802% potassium ferricyanide added = 2 c.c.

Control tube.	Volume of hypo required With blood sugar.	Conc. of Hypo	Sugar in blood (A-B) × strength × 0.177*
1.745 c.c.	1.155 c.c.	1.0126 N/200	0.1057%
1.745	1.155	1.0126 N/200	0.1057
1.75	1.17	1.01 N/200	0.1037
1.75	1.18	1.01 N/200	0.1019
1.65	1.25	1.036 N/200	0.07336
1.65	1.25	1.036 N/200	0.07336

In conclusion we wish to express our sincere thanks and gratitude to Mr. P. B. Sen for his kind assistance in the estimation of blood sugar and to Prof. Dr. H. K. Sen, for the interest which he has taken and the occasional help and advice he has so kindly given throughout the progress of the work.

DEPARTMENT OF APPLIED CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY, CALCUTTA.

Received March 31, 1936.

* *Biochem. Z.*, 1923, 135, 46 ; 137, 92.